

IRON AND MANGANESE REQUIREMENTS OF THE HUMAN ADULT.

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The average daily excretion of iron in those cases in which the experimental subjects (two adult men) were nearly in iron equilibrium was 10.2 mg. and 8.6 mg. respectively. Urinary iron excretions varied between 1.5 and 0.783 mg. per day.

Addition of calcium in the form of milk had no effect on iron retentions. The amount of so-called available iron in the food as measured by the dipyriddy method bore no relation to the amount absorbed.

Manganese was almost entirely eliminated along with the faeces. The average requirement for balance was 3.7, 3.8 and 5.5 mg. respectively in the case of three adult men.

Experiments on the amount of food-iron necessary for the maintenance of equilibrium have been very few in number. Sherman ("Chemistry of Food and Nutrition," 1937) summarises the data on iron requirement of normal human adults investigated in twenty-one cases and suggests that an average intake of about 8 mg. of iron per day is needed for men and women. It is necessary to study iron metabolism in more subjects before definite conclusions can be drawn with regard to iron requirements. It will also be interesting to investigate if there is a relation between the intake of available iron as measured by the dipyriddy method (Elvehjem *et al*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 103, 61) and the amount of iron utilised by human beings.

Manganese is a normal constituent of practically all tissues and plays specific rôles in metabolism. Investigations from McCollum's laboratory (Orent and McCollum, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 92, 651) show that manganese is an essential element from the stand-point of nutrition. It has been generally held that the amounts of manganese required per day are so small that an ordinary diet cannot be deficient in this element. It is, however, desirable to determine the minimal amount of manganese in the daily diet necessary for the maintenance of equilibrium in man. No studies in manganese requirements of human adults appear to have been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experiments on iron metabolism were performed on two healthy adults (men) S. N. D. (24 years, weighing 49 kilos) and U. C. S. (30 years, weighing 48 kilos). Experiments on manganese requirements were performed on the same two individuals and also on G. C. N. (19 years,

weighing 49 kilos). They lived with and were kept under the strict supervision of one of the authors (M.C.M.). They too realised the importance of the investigations, co-operated whole-heartedly in the work, led a strictly disciplined life during the periods of experiment and took nothing but the weighed amounts of food daily supplied to them. The composition of the diets is indicated later. In each series of experiments the cereal and pulse were taken from the same stock every day; aliquots of vegetables, fish and milk taken daily were pooled for analysis. With one particular diet the experimental subjects were daily given carefully weighed diets which they consumed *in toto* in two portions. In certain experiments only distilled water was used for drinking and cooking purposes. In those cases where tap water was employed the iron content of the water was taken into consideration. Tap water does not contain manganese in appreciable amounts. Each diet was taken for 6 or 9 days; the first three days were considered as a preliminary period to avoid any effect produced by the previous diet. Urine was collected quantitatively for 24 hour periods and the faeces for three days were collected together since the daily dry weight of the faeces was found to vary considerably. Faeces were marked by carmine.

After this six or nine day period on a particular diet, the effect of supplementing the diet with 275 c.c. of milk daily was observed for 6 days, urine being daily collected and analysed, while faeces for three day periods were collected together.

Since iron metabolism was being studied special precautions were taken. A special glass room was constructed in the laboratory where all the analyses of iron were performed. All possible sources of contamination with iron were avoided. Tripod stands and the wires in the fireclay triangles were made of copper. Aluminium utensils were used for cooking purposes and excrete were collected in aluminium vessels and dried over an aluminium dish in a room specially made to avoid contamination with iron.

Total iron was estimated by the thiocyanate method (Farrar, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, **110**, 685) and the available iron in foodstuffs by the *aa'*-dipyridyl method of Hill (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, **B**, **107**, 207) developed by Elvehjem, Hart and Sherman (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, **103**, 61).

Manganese was estimated by the method of Skinner and Peterson (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **88**, 347). Only traces of manganese were eliminated in urine.

All the experimental subjects were in nitrogen balance on the diets employed.

R E S U L T S.

The first experiment was performed on S. N. D. who took polished rice (550 g.), lentil (60 g.), vegetables (200 g.), fish (*Labeo rohita*) (65 g.), butter-fat (30 g.) and distilled water *ad libitum* per day. The diet was taken for 12 days, 275 c.c. of milk being added during the last 6 days. First three days and also the first three days of the milk diet were taken as preliminary periods and no collections were made on these days. Iron and manganese metabolism on this diet is indicated in Table I. In this and in the following tables figures of intake and output represent daily averages.

TABLE I.

Experimental subject: S. N. D.

Day of expt.	Iron metabolism.				Manganese metabolism.				
	Total dietary iron.	Available dietary iron.	Urinary iron.	Faecal iron.	Total iron output.	Balance.	Total dietary Mn.	Faecal Mn.	Balance.
4th			1.5 mg.						
5th			1.6						
6th			1.5						
Mean	14.0 mg.	7.9 mg.	1.5	9.3 mg.	10.8 mg.	3.2 mg.	6.9 mg.	6.0 mg.	0.9 mg.
(Diet & milk)									
10th			1.7						
11th			1.4						
12th			1.3						
Mean	14.54	7.9	1.5	9.3	10.8	3.7	6.9	5.3	1.6

The second experiment was also performed on S. N. D. who was daily given highly polished rice (550 g.) to diminish the intake of iron, lentil (60 g.), vegetables (200 g.), fish (*Labeo rohita*) (50 g.), sugar (100 g.), mustard oil (30 g.) and distilled water *ad libitum*. The diet was taken for 12 days, 275 c.c. of milk being added during the last 6 days. The first three days were taken as a preliminary period. The iron and manganese metabolism on this diet is indicated in Table II.

TABLE II.

Experimental subject : S. N. D.

Day of expt.	Iron metabolism.					Manganese metabolism.			
	Total dietary iron.	Available dietary iron.	Urinary iron.	Faecal iron.	Total iron output.	Balance.	Total dietary Mn.	Faecal Mn.	Balance.
4th			1.0 mg.						
5th			1.6						
6th			1.0						
Mean	9.0 mg.	6.6 mg.	1.2	11.7 mg.	12.9 mg.	-3.9 mg.	4.2 mg.	3.8 mg.	0.4 mg.
(Diet & milk)									
7th			0.8.						
8th			0.9						
9th			0.7						
Mean	9.5	6.6	0.8	9.6	10.4	-0.9	4.2	3.3	0.9
(Diet & milk)									
10th			0.8						
11th			0.8						
12th			0.8						
Mean	9.5	6.6	0.8	8.0	8.8	+0.7	4.2	4.1	0.1

The third experiment was performed on U. C. S. The composition of the diet was as follows :—Rice (coarse) (600 g.), lentil (60 g.), vegetables (200 g.), fish (*Labeo rohita*) (70 g.), mustard oil (30 g.), sugar (50 g.) and tap water. The diet was taken for 12 days, 275 c.c. of milk being added during the last 6 days. First three days were taken as a preliminary period. Iron and manganese metabolism of this diet is indicated in Table III.

TABLE III.

Experimental subject : U. C. S.

Day of expt.	Iron metabolism.					Manganese metabolism.			
	Total dietary iron.	Available dietary iron.	Urinary iron.	Faecal iron.	Total iron output.	Balance.	Total dietary Mn.	Faecal Mn.	Balance.
4th			1'04 mg.						
5th			1'2						
6th			1'2						
Mean	19'56 mg.	15'36 mg.	1'14	7'77 mg.	8'91 mg.	10'65 mg.	6'6 mg.	4'9 mg.	1'7 mg.
(Diet & milk)									
7th			1'12						
8th			1'28						
9th			1'05						
Mean	20'1	15'36	1'15	7'21	8'36	11'74	6'6	6'1	0'5
(Diet & milk)									
10th			0'75						
11th			1'02						
12th			1'0						
Mean	20'1	15'36	0'92	7'5	8'4	11'68	6'6	5'4	1'2

The fourth experiment was also performed on U. C. S. He was daily given whole wheat (500 g.), horse gram (70 g.), vegetables (180 g.), butter-fat (30 g.), sugar (50 g.) and tap water. The diet was taken for fifteen days, 275 c.c. of milk being given during the last 6 days. First three days were taken as a preliminary period. The iron and manganese metabolism on this diet is indicated in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Experimental subject: U.C.S.

Day of expt.	Iron metabolism.						Manganese metabolism.		
	Total dietary iron.	Available dietary iron.	Urinary iron.	Faecal iron.	Total iron output.	Balance.	Total dietary Mn.	Faecal Mn.	Balance
4th			0.6 mg.						
5th			0.79						
6th			0.91						
Mean	25.03 mg.	10.02 mg.	0.78	17.1 mg.	17.88 mg.	7.15 mg.	22.5 mg.	12.0 mg.	10.5 mg.
7th			0.85						
8th			0.80						
9th			0.85						
Mean	25.03	10.02	0.83	16.99	17.82	7.21	22.5	13.9	8.6
(Diet & milk)									
10th			0.78						
11th			0.80						
12th			0.87						
Mean	25.58	10.02	0.82	16.64	17.45	8.12	22.5	13.6	8.0
(Diet & milk)									
13th			0.86						
14th			0.77						
15th			0.84						
Mean	25.58	10.02	0.82	15.09	15.9	9.6	22.5	10.0	11.6

The fifth experiment in which only manganese metabolism was studied was performed on G.C.N. He was daily given polished rice (550 g.), lentil (60 g.), vegetables, (200 g.), fish (*Labeo rohita*) (70 g.), mustard oil (30 g.) and distilled water *ad libitum*. The diet was taken for 15 days, 275 c.c. of milk being added during the last 6 days. First three days were taken as preliminary period. Manganese metabolism on this diet is indicated in Table V.

TABLE V.

Experimental subject : G.C.N.

Day of expt.	Total dietary manganese.	Urinary manganese.	Faecal manganese.	Balance.
4th		Trace		
5th		"		
6th		"		
Mean	4.5 mg.	"	3.7 mg.	0.8 mg.
7th		"		
8th		"		
9th		"		
Mean	4.5	"	3.3	1.2
(Diet & milk)				
10th		"		
11th		"		
12th		"		
Mean	4.5	"	4.1	0.4
(Diet & milk)				
13th		"		
14th		"		
15th		"		
Mean	4.5	"	4.2	0.3

The sixth experiment on manganese metabolism was also performed on G.C.N. He was daily given whole wheat (550 g.), horse gram (70 g.), vegetables (180 g.), butter-fat (30 g.), sugar (60 g.) and tap water. The diet was taken for 15 days, 275 c.c. of milk being added during the last 6 days. First three days were taken as a preliminary period. Manganese metabolism on this diet is indicated in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Experimental subject: G.C.N.

Day of expt.	Total dietary manganese	Urinary manganese	Faecal manganese.	Balance.
4th		Trace		
5th		"		
6th		"		
Mean	21.4 mg.	"	14.9 mg.	6.5 mg.
7th		"		
8th		"		
9th		"		
Mean	21.4	"	16.9	4.5
(Diet & milk)				
10th		"		
11th		"		
12th		"		
Mean	21.4	"	19.9	1.5
(Diet & milk)				
13th		"		
14th		"		
15th		"		
Mean	21.4	"	18.0	3.4

DISCUSSION.

In the following table the iron outputs in those cases in which balance was nearly attained have been collected together.

TABLE VII.

Iron outputs near balance.

Experimental subjects.	Iron output near equilibrium.	Mean iron requirement.	Reference to data.
S.N.D. (49 kilo)	10.8 mg.		Table I
	10.8		" "
		10.2 mg.	" "
	10.4		" II
	8.8		" "
U.C.S. (48 kilo)	8.9		Table III
	8.4	8.6	" "
	8.4		" "

The mean iron requirement was thus 10.2 mg. in one case and 8.6 mg. in the other case. The mean of these two results is 9.4 mg., a value which is nearer to the previously recommended value of 10 mg. of Sherman (*loc.cit.*) It would also appear from the data on iron metabolism that the so-called available iron as measured by the *aa'*-dipyridyl method has very little effect on iron retentions. A reference to the metabolism studies would also show that supplementation with milk and hence with calcium has got little favourable effect on the retention of iron as was observed by Sherman (*loc. cit.*) and by Orlin, Smith and Mendel (*J. Nutrition.*, 1935, 12, 373).

On wheat diets the manganese intakes were far in excess of requirement while the experimental subjects were nearly in manganese equilibrium on rice diets. It is interesting to note that the whole of the manganese was excreted along with the faeces and only traces could be detected in the urine. The outputs near balance points are indicated below.

TABLE VIII.

Manganese outputs near balance.

Experimental subjects.	Manganese output near equilibrium.	Mean manganese requirement.	Reference to data
S.N.D. (49 kilo)	3.8 mg.		Table II
	3.3	3.7 mg.	"
	4.1		"
G.C.N. (49 kilo)	3.7		Table V
	3.3		"
	4.1	3.8	"
	4.2		"
U.C.S. (48 kilo)	4.9		Table III
	6.1	5.5	"
	5.4		"

The mean manganese requirement for balance is thus 3.7 mg. per day in one case and 3.8 mg. and 5.5 mg. in two other cases. The mean of these values is 4.6 mg. per day. In none of the twenty metabolism experiments recorded in this paper was a negative manganese balance obtained. Milk contains only traces of manganese and its addition to diets does not affect manganese metabolism.